

RAPD and PBR analysis of CMS maintainer and restorer lines in rice

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Recently developed molecular tools such as randomly amplified polymorphic DNA (RAPD) and polymerase chain reaction-based random fragment

length polymorphism (PBR) are available for characterizing genetic variation and DNA typing of rice genotypes. DNA analysis of three cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines with the respective maintainers (B) and two restorer lines (R) using 12 decamer primers from Operon (OPA-01 to OPA-12) revealed polymorphism only with primers OPA-03, OPA-07, OPA-09, and OPA-12. CMS lines IR67684A, IR58025A, and IR62829A have distinct

RAPD markers in contrast to their B and R lines. DNA polymorphism of A, B, and R lines was also confirmed with PBR in 15 primer/enzyme combinations. PBR reaction amplified a 546-bp (OPA-12) fragment in IR58025A and an 872-bp (OPA-12) fragment in IR62829A lines in a genotype-specific manner. These markers are being developed for identifying genotype-specific DNA markers and mapping desirable genes for hybrid rice research. ■

Transferring wild abortive cytoplasmic male sterility through asymmetric fusion of protoplasts

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We attempted a one-step transfer of wild abortive cytoplasmic male sterility (CMS) through asymmetric fusion between the protoplasts of CMS and fertile maintainer lines. We established embryogenic cell suspensions from the calli obtained from mature seed scutella of a CMS line (V20A), fertile

maintainers (RCPL1-2C and V20B), and restorer IR36 lines. We isolated and cultured protoplasts to produce protocalli that differentiated into plants. Pollen grains of the protoplast-derived plants of the CMS line were sterile, whereas those derived from the maintainer and restorer lines were fertile. To accomplish asymmetric fusion, the protoplasts of the CMS line and fertile maintainer lines were inactivated with 30 krad gamma ray and 10 mM iodoacetamide, respectively. Electrically fused protoplasts divided on a culture medium and formed micro-colonies that developed into calli. These calli also differentiated on transfer to a regeneration medium. We recovered 27 hybrid lines from the fusion product of V20A/RCPL1-2C and 23 lines from

V20A/V20B. Pollen grains from all the hybrid lines were sterile.

Analyses of mitochondrial DNA of the fusion partners and cybrids were conducted by using *orf156* as a probe. This revealed differences in polymorphism between the mitochondrial DNA of the CMS line and fertile maintainers. In the case of *HindIII*-digested DNA, the *orf156* gene was located on a 1.3-kb fragment in the male sterile line, V20A, and on a 12-kb fragment in its fertile maintainers, RCPL1-2C and V20B. A DNA blot analysis of the *HindIII*-digested DNA of all five cybrids showed hybridization of *orf156* to the 1.3-kb fragment. This demonstrated the transfer of mitochondrial DNA from the CMS line to the cybrids. ■

Breeding methods

Adaptability and yield of rice hybrids

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Heterosis in rice was reported in 1926. But commercial exploitation took almost 5 decades mainly because of problems in hybrid seed production. China was the only country to commercially exploit heterosis before 1994. Recently, a few rice hybrids were released in India for commercial cultivation. Although the yield advantage

of rice hybrids is well documented, doubts regarding their yield gains and adaptability over locations still persist. Therefore, we present here the average yield gains obtained from hybrids and their adaptability to locations in India. We used data from 1991 to 1995 on various hybrids tested under different trials over 12 locations in the wet season (WS) and at six locations during the dry season (DS). The yearwise mean yields of hybrids over locations and over trials were calculated separately for both the WS and DS. We identified a hybrid as widely adaptable if it had an overall yield advantage of more than 0.7 t ha⁻¹ over the high-

yielding national check variety Jaya, and we calculated the frequency of such hybrids for each season and year. Percentage heterosis was computed for each year based on the highest yielding hybrid vs Jaya.

The results showed that the overall mean of experimental hybrids increased gradually during the WS from 4.5 t ha⁻¹ in 1991 to 5.5 t ha⁻¹ in 1995; during the DS, yields increased similarly from 5.0 to 6.0 t ha⁻¹. During the same period, the percentage of widely adaptable hybrids in the WS increased from zero to 17%. Similarly, in the DS, it increased from 1.75% (1991-92) to 17% (1994-95). The